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**MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND
NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT**

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**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES OF
SINGAPORE COMMUNITY TOWARDS PLASTIC REDUCTION EFFORTS OF THE
GOVERNMENT**

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Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Singapore Community Towards Plastic Reduction Efforts of the Government

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Acceptance Page:

This Special Project titled: "**Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Singapore Community towards Plastic Reduction Efforts of the Government**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Ayessa Mae D. Gimutao

Acknowledgement

My UPOU journey started with curiosity. After graduating from UPLB as a Chemist, I spent most of my career years as a Chemistry Laboratory Analyst and there came a day when I was so swamped with work but it was this other aspect of work that I couldn't brush-off – our daily consumption of laboratory consumables in massive quantity and I began to wonder how the environment was coping from all these wastes so my curiosity got the best of me and I started digging. Aghast was an understatement to what I felt after reading articles and watching documentaries there available online regarding our environmental situation, and these really got to me. I was then reformed into an environmentally mindful individual and what better way to gain more knowledge on the matter but to opt for further studies. That's when UPOU came in. I learned from my peers that UPOU offers this program, MENRM, and my propulsion to file for an application rooted from my previous managers' uninspiring style of leadership. So to you my previous managers, my heartfelt gratitude. Though it's a cliché, truly, everything happens for a reason. There are so many people worth thanking for so let me start off with the UPOU admission committee who approved my application. I had naught hint of the criteria for selection but please know that I'm sincerely honoured to fit the bill, thank you. To my previous supervisors who went out of their way to fill up the letter of recommendations to help me get through, Mr. Wong Wai Ming, my Wyeth Nutrition Singapore supervisor and Ms. Hafel Ang, my Siltronic Singapore supervisor and now my friend, my earnest appreciation. I was actually unemployed when I got in but I was in constant hunt for a new job while several doors opened for me in the process, and I ventured on taking diverse challenges while attending to my UPOU tasks which proved arduous to say the least.

This journey became even more onerous the moment COVID-19 pandemic emerged or that's what I thought. Consequently, the pandemic led to several episodes of lockdown which apparently helped me focus on submitting my requirements for the courses. It appeared that the pandemic worked to my advantage at one point, helping me propel and advance on my MENRM courses, just because I got the support and help I required from my friends and family especially my husband who was patient enough and gracious all throughout. While prowling at the edge of failure due to the circumstances the world was facing, I managed to trudge through the pandemic but not without another ordeal. I was hired again in Singapore while I was at the last year of my courses which almost halted my UPOU journey due to time constraint. I painstakingly squeezed in my UPOU time amidst my wearisome work hours to impel myself and reach this point, thanks to my present supervisor. All my missed work hours to accomplish my UPOU duties were well received which I know were distressing sometimes due to the demands of our already lean work team. I'm gratified by your understanding and generosity Ms. Chin Lee Juan and my colleagues who had no choice but to cover for me. Thank you, Monika, our interns and contract personnel. To all my ex-colleagues and friends in Singapore who allocated precious time and efforts in distributing my survey, thank you. Special mention to Papa Miller, Mama Helen, Team Banta, my SG best friend Cherry aka Mic, our constant fourth member Ethel, and of course my husband Allan who worked the hardest in collecting my survey responses, I am indebted to all of you.

Now, I'm writing my acknowledgement for this paper, hopeful that I'll wear the UP Sablay this coming December, please allow me to address all my professors, mentors, all UPOU staff, from the admission, registration, IT, library and student support and FIC Dr. Consuelo de Luna Habito who made all these possible. From the

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Abstract

A survey was conducted among residents of Singapore to assess their knowledge, attitude and practices towards plastic reduction efforts of the government. There are numerous programs and policies being implemented to address the issue on plastic waste, even more on general waste in Singapore but significant members of the public seem to lack awareness on everything that's being implemented and not, how are these programs and policies being implemented and what should be done to comply and engage with them, though their willingness to take part in all these are unquestionable based on a previous study. Some of the government's efforts are palpable in the community such as the Mandatory Packaging Reporting (MPR) agreement with the packaged products producers which is the key for the implementation of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) framework for managing end-of-life packaging by the packaging products producers themselves, and reducing the use of disposable carrier bags from all major supermarkets island wide wherein disposable carrier bags are chargeable to consumers, while other programs are not widely known, but whether the effects of all these efforts are significant remain uncertain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Singapore recorded about 1.67 million tonnes of disposed waste in the year 2017 which came from domestic sources, about one-third constitutes packaging waste consisted of single-use disposables such as food packaging and plastic bags (National Environment Agency [NEA], 2018). While in 2016, a total of 822,200 tonnes of plastic waste was generated, 7% of which was only recycled, partly due to the complex nature of plastic waste mixtures – with presence of impurities, that mechanical method of recycling is inefficient and not widely preferred (Khoo, 2019). Only 4% of the total generated plastic waste in Singapore was recycled in 2019, but targets a 70% overall recycling rate by 2030 as one of the aims of Zero Waste Masterplan (oecd.org, n.d.). According to the World Economic Forum in 2016, plastic usage in the past 50 years has increased by twenty-fold, and in the next 20 years is expected to double (Ahamed et al., 2021). Most marine plastics end up in the sea due to enormous reasons like illegal or improper disposal, inadequate wastewater filtering, or natural disasters, hence the need to address marine plastics pollution through land-based initiatives (oecd.org, n.d.). The benefits in using plastic, such as plastic bags in convenience stores and supermarkets seem to outweigh the use of other viable alternative material, hence it is challenging to replace plastics in the near future (Ahamed et al., 2021). However, continuous plastic production over several decades gives rise to huge plastic waste generation around the world, which translates to exploitation of large amount of crude oil for the production, which has become a threat to society with the problems in disposal and emission of greenhouse gases (Sakthipriya, 2022).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Plastics. Plastic is versatile and one of the most commonly used substances in the twentieth century, which has replaced metal, wood and glass, and invaded industries of construction, clothing, food, shelter, transportation, medical, sports and a lot more, with its multiple properties – stability, durability, lightweight, low cost and unbreakable nature, paving the way to its wider application (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019). Plastics are synthetic or semisynthetic amorphous substances resembling the natural resins from plants and trees, are products of polymerization through both processes of condensation and addition giving rise to a long chain of monomers which requires huge amount of fossil fuel resources and energy to produce (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019). Many similar or equal subunits bonded together forming a large molecule is a polymer, which can either be man-made such as Parkesine or celluloid - the first man-made polymer, or naturally occurring, like silk, rubber, muscle fiber, cellulose and DNA (Geyer, 2020). There are several ways to categorize a polymer: one is the distinction between thermosets from thermoplastics (Geyer, 2020). Thermoplastics are recyclable as they harden once cooled and melt when heated, hence the solidity is changed as heat is applied and can be repeatedly done in both directions, while thermosets when heated undergo chemical change by forming an irreversible three-dimensional network, therefore, cannot be reformed and remelted which cause major recyclability issues (Geyer, 2020). Other way of categorizing plastics is in terms of carbon source – biobased plastic and fossil-based plastic (Geyer, 2020). Although compounds of natural gas are the major feedstock for fossil-based plastics, they are still sometimes called petroleum-based plastics, and none of the currently produced fossil-based plastics are considered biodegradable in the sense

that the timescales they biodegrade are significant for their end-of-life management (Geyer, 2020). Concurrently, it is also not proper to assume that all these biobased plastics are biodegradable as there are growing amount of biobased plastics chemically identical to one of the fossil-based polymers – PET or PE, hence shares the property of being non-biodegradable, with the sole difference of biobased PET or PE is having all or some of the chemical feedstock derived from biomass such as sugarcane or corn (Geyer, 2020). The buoyancy of plastics spreads them to a wider area for a long time while the polymer's versatility resulted to its generation in huge amount, and the material from which they are created from makes them resistant to degradation hence its perpetual presence when disposed of in open dumps and landfills (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019).

Plastic waste. Generation of plastic waste relies on lifestyle, increasing population, developmental activities and socioeconomic background, that more plastic waste generation is a result of higher consumption, hence, higher production, which can be categorized into industrial and municipal plastic waste (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019). Industrial wastes which are generated from the packaging, processing and manufacture of plastic products are considered homogenous, while municipal waste is heterogeneous which consists of disposable cups, wrappers, toys, plastic bags, vending cups, CD, wires and others, which, according to Panda *et al.* (2010) are discarded as household waste (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019).

Plastic waste started gaining traction due to its health and environmental hazards with the marine environment being largely impacted by plastics (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019). Persistent plastic-coated organic pollutants might harm the human beings and animals through their entry into the food chain such that animals die with stomach bloating problems and indigestion caused by plastic consumption along with

food, additionally, marine animals die of suffocation due to entanglement with plastics (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019). Burning of plastics release dioxin leading to cancer (Yogalakshmi and Singh, 2019). So what should be done to minimize if not eliminate these incessant impacts of plastic waste?

Plastic waste management. Developing countries have acute problem in dealing with both unmanaged and mismanaged municipal solid waste including plastic waste attributed to absence of equitable allocation of the economic resources, environmental injustice due to plastic waste disposal of the developed world, lack of infrastructure, systemic poverty, and many instances of non-existent accountability, equitable, and effective political capacity and governance (Browning, Beymer-Farris & Seay, 2021). For these reasons, it is a big challenge for developing countries to establish a successful, efficient and effective management program on municipal solid waste at a national scale as huge amounts of time, money and support are required which they lack (Browning *et al.*, 2021).

Reprocessing end-of-life products or their components for the purpose of reusing them is one way of managing plastic waste, which may include activities such as remanufacturing, refurbishing, repair or reconditioning, but essentially, reuse is not practiced (Geyer, 2020). On the other hand, recycling is the process of recovering the end-of-life material or waste product, so recycling of plastic waste is its reprocessing into recycled or secondary plastic, which can be classified into mechanical recycling of thermoplastics, the major plastic recycling process, chemical recycling which converts back plastic waste into its monomers through depolymerisation, a very limited process, and other methods that are still being developed (Geyer, 2020). Plastic-to-fuel technologies like gasification and pyrolysis destroy plastic thermally, but due to being costly, thermal destruction to date has been conducted through incineration

which can be done with or without the recovery of energy (Geyer, 2020). The ultimate destination of plastic waste is managed landfills, natural environment or open dumps, and the only way to clear away plastic from Earth is through thermal destruction since recycling only delays the inevitable – disposal (Geyer, 2020).

Below is the recommended waste hierarchy in Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata's (2012) report, generally accepted in the waste management sector.

Figure1. Waste hierarchy (Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012, p. 27).

*As a minimum, waste should be disposed at a "controlled dump," which includes site selection, controlled access, and where practical, compaction of waste. Incineration requires a complimentary sanitary landfill, as bottom ash, non-combustibles and by-passed waste needs to be landfilled.

This hierarchy responds to environmental, financial, social and management considerations, and also encourages GHG emissions minimization (Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012).

Initiatives to reduce source or waste aim to minimize waste at points of generation by changing patterns of consumption and production or redesigning products, to which reduction in GHG emission may come in a two-fold benefit: 1) emissions from product and material manufacture are avoided; and 2) emissions from

avoided waste management activities are eliminated (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012).

Recycling and recovery of materials help reduce the disposed waste quantities and material return to economy, that in various developing countries, informal waste pickers at disposal sites and collection points recover significant discard portions (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Alternatively, aerobic composting is an option, wherein composting can be done in enclosed vessels or windrows to prevent methane formation associated with anaerobic conditions, which leads us to a process called anaerobic digestion in treating organic waste in an enclosed vessel generating methane that can be utilized to generate heat and/or electricity (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012).

Waste incineration along with energy recovery can help reduce the disposed waste volume by up to 90%, which can only be seen in waste streams of very high amounts of paper, packaging materials, plastics, cardboard and horticultural waste, and considered preferable to landfilling provided costs and pollution control requirements are adequately addressed (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Incineration without energy recovery is not the recommended option due to pollution and costs, and open-burning is discouraged as it can cause risks of severe air pollution (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012).

Finally, landfills are common terminal disposal sites for waste and should be operated and engineered to protect public health and environment (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012).

Singapore and the world. Waste volumes are quickly increasing globally even faster than urbanization rate, with the fastest Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) growth rates in China, parts of Middle East and Eastern Europe, and other parts of East Asia

(Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Solid waste generation is linked to economic development and urbanization, that as economic wealth increases, disposable incomes and standards of living increase, services and goods consumption also increases resulting to the increase in generated waste (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Urban residents generate about twice as much as their rural counterparts (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). It is estimated as to the time of writing the report that 1.3 billion tons of MSW are generated per year globally or 1.2 kg/capita/day (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012).

With the country classification according to region, Singapore is under East Asia & Pacific (EAP) together with China, Malaysia, Thailand and Philippines, while it is considered a High Income Country (HIC) according to this report by Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata (2012). The waste generation in EAP is estimated to be 270 million tons per year with China making up 70% of the total, per capita ranges from 0.44 to 4.3 kg/person/day with 0.95 kg/capita/day average according to Hoorweg *et al.* (2005) (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Globally, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) region comprising of South Korea, Japan, UK, USA, European and other countries, takes up almost half of the global waste, while South Asia and Africa are the regions with the least waste (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). On the other hand, HIC countries including Singapore produce the most per capita waste, while low income countries (LIC) generate the least (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Though Singapore is not included in the world's top 20 countries marine plastic waste sources – the list includes Indonesia, Philippines, China, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Malaysia, India and Thailand from Asia-Pacific region, according to Jambeck *et al.*, the country's plastic recycling rate is still less than 10% attributed to overpackaging, consumer habits and use of plastic bags (Akenji *et al.*, 2020).

According to NEA (n.d.), there were around 6.94 million tonnes of generated solid waste in Singapore from which 3.83 million tonnes were recycled in 2021 with the plastic waste recycling rate increase from 4 per cent in 2020 to 6 per cent in 2021. COVID-19 impacted both waste generation and recycling rates which were both lower in 2020, while 2021 demonstrated a 10 per cent increase in disposed waste and 26 per cent more waste recycled as economic activity picked up (NEA, n.d.).

III. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

There are several Singapore government agencies and ministries that are involved in tackling marine plastics pollution (oecd.org, n.d.). One of them is the Ministry of Sustainability and the Environment (MSE) with the responsibility of ensuring climate resilience, resource resilience and economic resilience (oecd.org, n.d.). The Environment Policy Division which is under the Ministry works towards the circular economy, zero waste and environmental protection (oecd.org, n.d.). NEA, which is both under the Energy and Climate Policy Division of the MSE and the Environment and Climate Policy Division has duties of ensuring a clean and green environment, promotion of the circular economy, sustainable development, solid waste management and the 3Rs, while the Maritime and Port Authority of Singapore (MPA) is responsible in ensuring security, environmental protection and safety in port waters (oecd.org, n.d.). Both MSE and NEA employed and plans to employ several programs to tackle the issues on plastic waste. The following are the policies and programs being implemented:

Resource Sustainability Act. This is the driving force behind the waste reduction plan of Singapore which lets companies be more responsible for the wastes generated after consumers used their products (Hicks, 2019). The purposes of this Act are: 1) to implement a framework wherein those who profit from the product supply bear the cost of treating and collecting these products when they turn into waste; 2) to encourage packaging producers to re-use, reduce or recycle packaging and; 3) to enable proper treatment and segregation of food waste (Singapore Statutes Online, 2019). The first measure for the Act is the mandatory reporting of companies that use or produce packaging by 2020, then they need to come up with a plan on reducing their packaging

footprint (Hicks, 2019).

Mandatory Packaging Reporting (MPR). As of 2020, packaged products producers must submit information on packaging material type, such as paper, glass, plastic, metal, etc., packaging weight, form of packaging such as bottles, cartons, carrier bags, cans, etc., and 3R plans such as packaging collection for recycling or reuse, packaging reduction, and use of recycled content in their packaging (oecd.org, n.d.). This program (MPR) will be the key for the implementation of the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) framework for management of packaging waste, wherein producers will be responsible for the management of their end-of-life packaging supplied in Singapore (NEA, 2022).

Zero Waste Masterplan. The 2019 Zero Waste Masterplan maps out the key strategies of Singapore to build a resource-efficient, sustainable and climate-resilient nation by working on key targets such as the reduction of waste sent to the only landfill of the nation – Semaku landfill daily by 30% by 2030 which can hopefully extend the landfill's lifespan beyond 2035, and plans to obtain an extended producer responsibility framework by 2025 (oecd.org, n.d.). The growing waste generation due to ramp up of economic activities urges the shift from linear to circular economy which is the key idea of Zero Waste Masterplan and Singapore Green Plan (NEA, n.d.). Singapore's key strategies include the circular economy approach to resource and waste management, and a switch towards more sustainable consumption and production (Towards Zero Waste, n.d.). Singapore follows three key principles as guides on waste management policies and these are: 1) environmental protection, economic development and social inclusion are all equally important; 2) to achieve the best outcome, everyone must work together; and 3) policies and plans should be cater to local context and focused on the long term, including an integrated approach to

achieve better resource efficiencies and synergies (Towards Zero Waste, n.d.). NEA targets a 70 percent national overall recycling rate and reduce to 30 percent the waste-to-landfill per capita per day by 2030, a goal frontloaded by a target of 20 percent reduction in waste-to-landfill per capita per day by the year 2026 to help fulfil the Singapore Green Plan 2030, and extend Singapore's landfill lifespan beyond 2035 (NEA, 2021/2022). Additionally, 2030 targets are also set to increase to 80 percent the non-domestic recycling rate and 30 percent domestic recycling rate (NEA, 2021/2022). The circular economy approach focuses on maximizing the resource value by keeping them in use for the longest possible time and designing waste out of the ecosystem resource (Towards Zero Waste, n.d.). The adoption of this approach requires measures including better product design, reducing the use of resources at production, revamp in consumer habits where products are repaired instead of replacing them with new ones, and waste recycling and reintroduction into the value chain (Towards Zero Waste, n.d.). Singapore has been adopting this approach in several areas – construction metals and waste are recycled, water loop has been closed by combining water and sanitation, recycling water endlessly allowing Singapore to reintroduce up to almost 800,000 m³ of ultra-pure recycled water daily into the system (Towards Zero Waste, n.d.).

3R Program. The 3Rs – Reduce (Use only what you need), Reuse (Re-use things for the same or new purpose) and Recycle (Convert waste into useful products), or otherwise known as waste minimization and recycling, are Singapore's key thrusts in its solid waste management system, and as a land-scarce country, waste-to-energy (WTE) incineration plants is the most preferred solution in waste reduction to conserve landfill space (NEA, nd). Most plastic wastes in Singapore are sent to WTE plants for two purposes: a) to reduce volumes of waste, and b) to derive energy in the form of

electrical power, wherein 1 tonne of plastic waste mixture generate an estimated 634 kW h of electrical power, 90% of which reduce waste volume and 10% are considered residual waste comprised of fly and bottom ash that are sent by barge to Pulau Semakau, Singapore's offshore landfill (Khoo, 2019). There are also waste recycling campaigns launched and actively promoted by regulatory organisations and authorities such as "Recycling Corner" and "Let's Recycle Together" and other measures that raise environmental awareness and encourage recycling of wastes (Zhou et al., 2022). This 3R Program branches out into multiple sector-specific and micro and other related programs and projects that aim to address the reduction if not elimination of plastic wastes in the whole region.

Singapore Green Plan 2030. This is a program that seeks to establish a nationwide movement and advance Singapore's agenda on sustainable development by charting concrete plans and targets for the rest of the decade consisting of five pillars – 1) Sustainable Living; 2) Energy Reset; 3) City in Nature; 4) Green Economy; and 5) Resilient Future (SG Green Plan, n.d.). Among the five, sustainable living is the most relevant to plastic waste as this pillar highlights targets on reducing carbon emissions and embracing sustainability by taking public transport, consuming less, and recycling more while working towards the vision on becoming a Zero Waste Nation through the circular economy approach, with "Reduce, Reuse and Recycle" to turn into a norm among citizens and businesses (SG Green Plan, n.d.).

National Recycling Programme. This program was launched in April 2001, requires the NEA licensed public waste collectors (PWCs) to administer recycling collection services and recycling bins to all HDB estates, condominiums / private apartments, and private landed properties covered by the public waste collection scheme (NEA, n.d.). Designated recycling trucks gather the mixed recyclables and

send them over to Materials Recovery Facilities (MRF) for sorting, which in turn are sent to recycling facilities for further processing (NEA, n.d.).

Integrated Waste Management Facility (IWMF). NEA in collaboration with Public Utilities Board (PUB) planned and developed IWMF in 2013 for a joint engineering study in evaluating the potential of harnessing processing synergies through a solid waste treatment facility co-location together with a used water reclamation facility which lead to co-location of these two mega facilities – Tuas Water Reclamation Plant and IWMF, now collectively known as Tuas Nexus, which will operationalize the water-energy-waste nexus to optimize use of land, and resource and energy recovery (NEA, 2021/2022). Developed in phases, the first phase comprised of the construction of Materials Recovery Facility (250 tons/day) and Waste-to-Energy Facility (2,900 tons/day) in May 2020, and Food Waste Treatment Facility (400 tons/day) and Sludge Incineration Facility (800 tons/day) in August 2021, which is expected to complete in 2025 to 2026, while Phase 2 which includes the construction of another waste-to-energy Facility (2,900 tons/day) will follow thereafter (NEA, 2021/2022).

Reducing the use of disposable carrier bags. Operators of supermarkets will be enforced to charge for the disposable carrier bags starting mid-2023 to encourage consumers to adopt sustainable habits of reducing the use of disposable bags and bringing their own bags while operators are highly encouraged to use the proceeds to support environmental or charitable causes (NEA, 2021/2022).

Other policies. Antilittering laws have been strictly adopted and implemented in the country, together with the promotion of practices on integrated waste management as mentioned above to reduce waste at source and make sure of proper waste disposal (Akenji *et al.*, 2020). Relevant legislation includes “Environmental Public Health Act” (1987); “Prevention of Pollution of the Sea (Garbage) Regulations” (1999);

and “National Environment Agency Act” (2002) (Akenji *et al.*, 2020). Prevention of Pollution of the Sea Act is a Singapore Act of Parliament that includes subsidiary legislation regarding garbage disposal (oecd.org, n.d.), and aims to prevent pollution of the sea whether land-based origin or from ships, and also provides power to Maritime and Port Authority (MPA) to implement preventive measures to prevent pollution which include entry denial or detaining of ships (mpa.gov.sg., n.d.). Additionally, the government has a growing concern on circular economy approaches and currently developing a suite of policies that will encourage sustainable production and consumption including the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) program that will start with electronic waste set to be implemented by 2021 (Akenji *et al.*, 2020).

NEA is also exploring chemical recycling solutions to end Singapore’s plastic waste loop by processing plastics that mechanical recycling method cannot process, such as those single-use plastics that are contaminated, converting these into products of higher value like pyrolysis oil which can be used as feedstock to manufacture new chemicals and plastics (NEA, 2021/2022). Other innovative solutions and efforts are also being developed and supported by the government through R&D projects to help close the waste and resource loops (NEA, 2021/2022).

Previous studies. An article published by Ipsos stated that in the survey they conducted, 55% of Singaporeans believed that climate change is the top environmental issue the local leaders should give the greatest attention to, and that 97% among Singaporeans accepted that climate change is partly influenced by human activity, while 78% recognize that their behaviour impacts the environment, that they take serious view especially the issue on the use of plastics (Ho, Causier and Karlsson, 2020). 79% of the Singaporeans acknowledge that use of plastics excessively is a problem and almost half (47%) admit to separating their plastic waste for recycling

(Ho, Causier and Karlsson, 2020). The reasons behind the recycling practice are: according to 47% of the Singaporeans, it's inconvenient to engage in environmentally friendly activities and only 26% are confident enough to interpret the recycling symbols printed on packaging (Ho, Causier and Karlsson, 2020).

On a survey conducted by PACT (Plastic ACTion) of WWF in November of 2018, 70% of Singaporeans are willing to recycle more if it was easier and more convenient to recycle, 60% would recycle more for cash incentive, 43% would do it if there are clear recyclable information printed on the packaging, and 33% would recycle more if the government has legislated it (Ho, Causier and Karlsson, 2020). To help reduce the problems caused by plastic waste that cannot be recycled, 35% are willing to halt their use of plastic bags, bottles and straws while 37% are willing to buy more products of recycled materials (Ho, Causier and Karlsson, 2020).

The Singapore Environment Council also conducted a survey in 2013 which showed a total of 3 billion plastic bags used in Singapore, and the plastic bag reuse rates among 2500 Singaporean respondents, from which, 44.1% reused around 6-10 bags weekly, 28.3% reused 5 bags or less per week and 5.3% reused more than 20 plastic bags on a weekly basis (WWF.sg, n.d.).

Knowledge, Attitude, Practices (KAP) surveys. By definition, **K**nowledge is a set of understandings, “science” and knowledge, which is also one’s way perceiving and one’s capacity for imagining (Gumucio *et.al.*, 2011). **A**ttitude is a position or a way of being, an intermediate position between a situation and a response to that situation, explains that among all possible practices for a subject who submitted to a stimulus, the subject adopts one practice and not the others, they are also leanings or “tendencies to...”, which are not directly observable like the practices (Gumucio *et.al.*, 2011). **P**ractices or behaviours on the other hand are observable concrete actions in

response to a stimulus (Gumucio *et al.*, 2011). According to Vandamme (2009), the KAP model was a popular survey instrument recognized and developed in the field of social research which originated from the fields of population and family planning studies in the 1950s, that can be used to evaluate the relationship among knowledge, attitudes and practices (Liao *et al.*, 2022). KAP surveys basically record “opinions” and are based on “declarative”, which exhibit misunderstandings or misconceptions that show obstacles to activities that are supposed to be implemented and probable barriers to behaviour change (United States Agency for International Development [USAID], n.d.). A KAP survey can establish reference or baseline value which can be useful for future assessments, measure the extent of a known variable or situation, disprove or confirm hypothesis, provide a situation’s reality new tangents, enhance the specific theme’s knowledge, attitude and practices, suggest an intervention strategy demonstrating cultural factors and local circumstances that influence them, and plan activities suitable to the correspondent population involved (USAID, n.d.).

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

- Evaluate the policies / programs that are effective and impactful to the community, that the intended purpose of the policies / programs cross the entire community efficiently and accurately.
- This study can be considered in deciding which policy / program can be sustained and improved, or how it can be improved so that more resident will engage in environment-friendly programs until they've adapted sustainable habits and attitudes in performing their daily activities.
- The study can be considered as a baseline of the Singapore government or even other countries in building their policy framework and development in managing not only plastic waste but overall disposed waste.

V. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Among the plethora of policies / programs employed in Singapore in managing their plastic waste, the question is, how much of these reach the public and what is the extent of their grasp on the concepts and ideas behind the implementing rules and programs of the government. This paper aimed to assess the knowledge or level of awareness, attitude, and practices of the community regarding plastic waste and Singapore government's efforts in reducing plastic waste and evaluate the impact, efficiency and effectivity of plastic waste reduction policies / programs to the community and environment.

VI. METHODOLOGY

To assess the level of awareness of the community regarding Singapore government's efforts in plastic waste reduction, a survey was conducted among Singapore residents through google form with this link: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1eTE5Q8MD5QJgJLNSc77_PfSqznduvsxwQnuHsHooawl/viewform?pli=1&pli=1&edit_requested=true#responses. Singapore residents were the Singaporeans, Permanent Residents (PRs), and work / long-term pass holders – Singapore-based workers and non-workers. There were seven (7) questions in the survey.

Figure 2. Questions 1 and 2 in the survey form.

The image shows two sections of a survey form. The first section is titled 'Age group you belong to' and has four radio button options: '25 and below', '26 - 40', '41 - 60', and '61 and above'. The second section is titled 'Social group' and has three radio button options: 'Student (undergraduate and/or graduate)', 'Working group (full and/or part-time)', and 'Non-working group'.

These first two questions were meant to shape a form of representation for one or more segments of the sample that the survey was able to reach. The responses here could be related to the survey results in some ways, whether age and employment status account for the differences and/or similarities in the way people behave and approach the plastic waste issue in Singapore.

Figure 3. Question 3 in the survey form.

Number of years residing in Singapore

0 - 5

6 - 20

21 and above

Question 3 aimed to determine if the duration of stay in Singapore was directly influencing the level of familiarity of the respondents with the government's policies in battling the issues of plastic waste in the nation.

Figure 4. Question 4 in the survey form.

National Environment Agency (NEA), in conjunction with other institutions, launched several programs, schemes and/or campaigns promoting environment sustainability and cleanliness in Singapore.

Among the choices below, please tick all that you are aware of or familiar with.

3Rs (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle)

Recycle N Save initiative (e.g. Reverse Vending Machines)

National Recycling Programme

Clean and Green Singapore

WasteCare

Question 4 was a test on the knowledge and level of familiarity of the respondents regarding the government's policies and programs on plastic waste and environment sustainability and cleanliness.

Figure 5. Questions 5 and 6 in the survey form.

What materials should be placed in the 'BLUE' recycling bins? Please tick all your answers.

- paper receipt
- pizza box
- toys
- perfume bottles
- aerosol can
- egg trays
- old medals
- plastic clothes hanger
- steel wool
- used clothing

What materials should NOT be placed in the blue bin which are considered general wastes? Please tick all your answers.

- crystal glass
- styrofoam
- glossy magazine
- crayon drawings
- wooden chopsticks
- metal bottle cap
- oven-safe food containers
- expired credit cards
- bubble wrap
- facial cleanser bottle

Questions 5 and 6 of the survey were intended to gauge and evaluate the knowledge and practices of the respondents in recycling waste products in Singapore.

Figure 6. Question 7 in the survey form.

If you are to assess yourself on how well you are practicing the Environmental Sustainability programs such as 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) in your daily activities, what will be your rank?

- 1 - I haven't started practicing it yet
- 2 - I'm quite inconsistent
- 3 - Good (I'm trying my best but I know I can do more)
- 4 - Excellent (I'm committed to protecting our environment)

The seventh question served two purposes - 1) to assess the attitude and behaviour of the respondents toward Singapore government's policies and programs on environmental sustainability especially plastic waste; and 2) to encourage them to engage more on these policies and programs if they haven't yet.

To evaluate the impact, efficiency and effectivity of plastic waste reduction efforts in the country, review of literatures was conducted, and survey with descriptive statistics was performed.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study is based on the knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) research model. A survey was conducted among Singaporean residents through google form to assess their level of awareness regarding the government's efforts in reducing plastic waste which garnered a total of 248 responses.

Figure 7. Summary of responses for questions 1 and 2 of the survey.

The 248 responses were equally dominated by two age groups – 26-40 and 41-60 with 45.6% responses each, hence a total of 91.2% responses from the 26-60 aged group which can be assumed to belong to the working group which garnered a 93.9% total response to question 2. According to the 2022 data by Department of Statistics Singapore, the total population in the country was 5,637,000, from which, 3,754,200 were included in the labour force, more than 66% of the entire population (Manpower Research & Statistics Department, n.d.). Labour force is defined as the economically active population or the currently available manpower in the economy which consists

of both the employed or working and unemployed or seeking work (Manpower Research & Statistics Department, n.d.). The majority of the respondents in the survey represented the major social group in Singapore which was the working population.

Figure 8. Summary of responses for question 3.

61.7% of the survey respondents had been living in Singapore for 21 years and above, while 94.8% had been residing in the country for at least six years. A classic assumption that majority of the respondents were familiar with the implementing rules and/or policies in Singapore regarding plastic waste and environmental sustainability could be justified by their length of stay in the country.

Figure 9. Summary of responses for question 4.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics for question 4

Question 4		Frequency	Number of years residing in Singapore			Total
			Responses in %			
			0 - 5	6 - 20	21 and above	
Which environmental sustainability program/s launched in Singapore are you aware of or familiar with?	3Rs	212	3.66	28.46	54.07	86.19
	Clean and Green Singapore	157	2.03	22.36	39.43	63.82
	National Recycling Program	154	1.22	21.54	39.84	62.60
	Recycle N Save	133	1.63	18.29	34.15	54.07
	WasteCare	33	1.22	6.91	5.28	13.41

WasteCare is a national recycling management company in the UK (wastecare, n.d.) and there were 33(13.41%) respondents who seemed unaware of that. The rest of the programs were launched in Singapore but almost half of the respondents were not familiar with Recycle N Save, while more than 85% were aware of the 3Rs program, yet it still didn't translate to the 6% plastic recycling rate of Singapore. Recycle N Save is a joint initiative by NEA and F&N to encourage recycling of used aluminium drink cans and plastic drink bottles and help the Singaporeans adopt an

eco-conscious lifestyle by providing them a convenient option to recycle, through placing 50 Smart Reverse Vending Machines (RVM) across the country (RecycleNSave, n.d.). RVM School Education Programme was also launched under Recycle N Save in March 2020 to inculcate recycling habits at a young age by placing RVMs in participating Primary and Secondary Schools (NEA, n.d.).

Figure 10. Summary of responses for question 5.

Table 2

Descriptive statistics for question 5

Question 5	Frequency	Number of years residing in Singapore			Total
		Responses in %			
		0 - 5	6 - 20	21 and above	
paper receipt	217	3.64	27.94	56.28	87.85
egg trays	194	1.62	23.89	53.04	78.54
pizza box	140	2.43	19.03	35.22	56.68
plastic clothes hanç	139	2.43	20.65	33.20	56.28
perfume bottles	130	1.62	19.43	31.58	52.63
toys	116	1.62	11.34	34.01	46.96
used clothing	105	0.81	12.15	29.55	42.51
old medals	88	2.02	13.77	19.84	35.63
steel wool	74	1.62	12.96	15.38	29.96
aerosol can	67	1.62	11.74	13.77	27.13

More than 50% of the respondents were not fully aware that pizza box should not be placed in the recycling bin while more than 40% each elected to place used clothing and toys in the recycling bin while they are classified as general waste. Pizza box is not considered recyclable as they are often unclean and used, hence can't be recycled, and may contaminate other recyclables, while toys are also not considered recyclables, and used clothing should be donated if in good condition, else, be disposed as general waste (NEA, n.d.).

Figure 11. Summary of responses for question 6.

Table 3

Descriptive statistics for question 6

Question 6	Frequency	Number of years residing in Singapore			Total	
		Responses in %				
		0 - 5	6 - 20	21 and above		
What materials should not be placed in the blue bin which are considered general wastes?	styrofoam	212	2.45	26.53	57.55	86.53
	expired credit card	170	1.22	21.22	46.94	69.39
	crystal glass	164	1.63	17.55	47.76	66.94
	crayon drawings	128	1.22	16.73	34.29	52.24
	wooden chopsticks	124	1.22	17.55	31.84	50.61
	oven-safe food containers	106	1.22	13.06	28.98	43.27
	facial cleanser bott	104	1.22	12.65	28.57	42.45
	bubble wrap	104	1.63	12.65	28.16	42.45
	metal bottle cap	82	1.22	8.98	23.27	33.47
	glossy magazine	66	1.22	5.31	20.41	26.94

recyclable materials

This question basically asked the respondents to identify the general wastes and the results were slightly better than that of question 5 as the recyclable wastes were picked by less respondents placing them at the bottom half of the ranking while it's noteworthy that almost 90% of the respondents considered Styrofoam as a general waste. Recycling Styrofoam can't be done in Singapore coz it's almost impossible to recycle it and there only few places in the world that can actually do it (recyclopeda.sg, 2023). Few businesses avoid taking it back due to hygiene concerns and it often ends up as litter making it a significant source of coastal marine pollution due to its lightness hence gets easily blown away and washed into waterways (recyclopeda.sg, 2023).

Figure 12. Summary of responses for question 7.

Question 7 was meant to assess the respondents' attitudes towards environmental sustainability programs such as 3Rs and to gauge their willingness in incorporating those programs into their daily activities and the result was not encouraging. Majority of the respondents (60.7%) admitted to being inconsistent in acting on the said programs while only 1.6% (4 of 247 responses) were committed to protecting our environment.

Responses to questions 4, 5 and 6, which were intended to assess both the knowledge and practices of respondents toward the Singapore government policies or

programs regarding plastic waste and/or environment sustainability proved mediocre, aligned to their responses to question 7 which demonstrated their inconsistent attitudes in engaging to environmentally sustainable practices. KAP questions tend to reveal the characteristic traits in knowledge, attitude and practices about the research, and also each person's idea about the topic, that the obstacle to behaviour change may be a lack of knowledge of the problem and its severity (Gumucio *et.al.*, 2011). In this case, insufficient know-how by the respondents about the implementing policies and guidelines regarding plastic waste reduction efforts by the government translated to their unsatisfactory practices and attitudes in adhering and engaging to them.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the survey, level of awareness, commitment and engagement were not high among the respondents in practicing the Singapore government's environment sustainability programs though based on a previous survey conducted by PACT of WWF (2018), 70% of Singaporeans were willing to recycle more if it would be easier and more convenient for them, but when and how will it be convenient for them is the question. Therefore, a potential barrier to the behaviour change of the respondents could be the inadequate and inefficient information dissemination of the government's environment sustainability programs specifically plastic waste reduction efforts and also, elucidation of the purposes and motivations behind these programs and policies. Equipping the people with proper knowledge of recycling and other environment sustainability principles while emphasizing the severity of the global and country's plastic waste situation could capitalize their willingness to recycle and get more involved with the programs. As majority of the country's population are in the working group tantamount to spending most of their time at work, the government must work hand in hand with the employers to efficiently relay to the working group the significance of knowing and acting upon all the programs and policies mentioned and inculcate them into their daily lives. It would also help to address the convenience of the people in complying with these programs and policies until environmentally sustainable practices are impelled into their everyday routine.

A 6% plastic recycling rate is rather low for a high income country (HIC) like Singapore though the country is still not among the top contributors in the world and the people's awareness, knowledge and attitude towards government's environment program, and the inadequate enforcement may have a lot to do with that. There may

be more than enough programs and policies there exist to effectively manage plastic and general waste in Singapore but this study has exhibited that huge room for improvement in heightening people's awareness and knowledge in managing plastic waste, stricter implementation of policies, and convey accurate and clear information to people which could be the solid and proper motivation for the community to act upon this seemingly unstoppable issue on plastic waste.

With enough resources and time, a well-represented population demographics in Singapore could be explored in future studies related to this research. Other methods of data collection maximizing the use of social media platforms such as Youtube, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram or Tiktok may also be considered to gain more attention from the youth while spreading awareness on environmental sustainability programs being implemented by the government.

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List of Appendices

Appendix 1

Google form questionnaire

Survey on Singapore's plastic waste

Sign in to Google to save your progress. Learn more

* Indicates required question

Email *

Your email _____

Name *

Your answer _____

Age group you belong to

25 and below

26 - 40

41 - 60

61 and above

Social group

Student (undergraduate and/or graduate)

Working group (full and/or part-time)

Non-working group

Number of years residing in Singapore

0 - 5

6 - 20

21 and above

National Environment Agency (NEA), in conjunction with other institutions, launched several programs, schemes and/or campaigns promoting environment sustainability and cleanliness in Singapore.

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What materials should NOT be placed in the blue bin which are considered general wastes? Please tick all your answers.

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styrofoam

glossy magazine

crayon drawings

wooden chopsticks

metal bottle cap

oven-safe food containers

expired credit cards

bubble wrap

facial cleanser bottle

If you are to assess yourself on how well you are practicing the Environmental Sustainability programs such as 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) in your daily activities, what will be your rank?

1 - I haven't started practicing it yet

2 - I'm quite inconsistent

3 - Good (I'm trying my best but I know I can do more)

4 - Excellent (I'm committed to protecting our environment)